

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND ITS ROLE IN HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Collecting the correct data in the dynamic world of industries and analysing the collected data is important for the use of business development and everyday work. Artificial Intelligence allows the industry to complete the job in a quicker and more efficient way. Artificial Intelligence joins various departments, such as Human Resources, Finance, Marketing and Production department. Through the use of AI system management, current output and everyday tasks can be told. Tough managers have acknowledged the value of artificial intelligence at workplace in growing market strain. There is a descriptive dimension to the research paper. Secondary data were used by the researcher where data were gathered from research papers, journals, websites, HR forums, survey results etc. The study's central objective was to explore the role of artificial intelligence in the human resource department and to recognize the issues facing HR. The research study concluded that AI's position is greater in various human resource functions where robotics companies can handle recruiting, hiring, data analysis, data processing, workload reduction and workplace performance enrichment.

Keywords: - Artificial Intelligence, Machine Languages, Human Resource Management.

1. Introduction

Technology is one of the Industry's main influencing factors. The position of the robot has been replacing employees in the production department since the 19th century. In the 1970s personal computers began in the third revolution and the internet entered into working life, and the machines replaced human labour. Today, emerging innovations such as machine language (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) are both reaching the day-to-day workplace and contributing to company transformation. "Artificial intelligence is described as an 'intelligent ideal' computer that is a versatile agent that perceives its environment and takes action that maximizes its chance of succeeding to some objective. "Artificial intelligence is intelligence demonstrated by machine, in contrast to the natural intelligence done by humans. Artificial intelligence was introduced first time in academia in 1956. Artificial intelligence is useful in various business functions where it can help reduce the workload and job pressure on workplace employees. Rapid market changes require a swift response. Through using AI system management, current output, and day to day work can be told. Tough managers have acknowledged the value of artificial

intelligence at the workplace in rising market strain. Artificial intelligence has now entered an organization's overall structure for a few days and one sector is the human resource department where human replaced the human by using AI technology and all roles in the human resource department are carried out as applicant screening, recruiting, human resource activation alignment and performance management, etc.

Figure: 1

Source: - (Duchessi, O'Keefe, & O'Leary, 1993)

A structure reveals the Artificial Intelligence relationship between management and the organization. The author of the research (Duchessi, O'Keefe, & O'Leary, 1993) discussed in the research article that artificial intelligence and digital technology have an impact on ownership and responsibility for decision making, cost reduction and enhanced service, personnel shifts and downsizing organizational organization, the control of the labour force.

2. Literature Review

(R&D,2018) The research paper title, Recruitment through artificial intelligence: A Conceptual Study. The researchers have narrated the role of AI in recruitment where artificial intelligence is played integral role in recruitment process. Artificial intelligence helps in screening the candidates, auto-generated messages to candidates, employee's relations, scheduling the interviewsetc.

(Jarrahi, 2018) In his researcher paper title, Artificial Intelligence and the Future of work: Human- AISymbiosis in Organizational Decision Making. The researcher papers talked about the usefulness of AI for human. Artificial intelligence has been supporting in decision making, dealing with uncertainty, and especially equivocality of decision-making in an organization. Still in an industry the role of human is essential and technologies have to depend on human when

subconscious decisions are essential to evaluate and facilitate the outcomes of decisions.

Table: 1

	Humans Mind	Artificial Intelligence
Uncertainty	Makes swift intuitive decisions in the face of unknown.	Provide access to “real time” information.
Complexity	Decide where to seek, and gather data. Choose among options with equal data support.	Collect, accurate, process, and analyze data.
Equivocality	Negotiate, build consensus, and rally support.	Analyze sentiments, and represent diverse interpretations.

Source: (Jarrahi, 2018)

(Merlin.P&Jayam.R, 2018) In the research title, Artificial Intelligence in Human Resource Management, the researcher has insight the role of AI in human resource. An Author has concluded that AI is useful in workplace and help to HR professional to understand their working and to identify the problems and trends in advance.

3. Research Objectives

1. To study the role of artificial intelligence in human resource management.
2. To study the Impact of artificial intelligence on HR technology
3. To study the benefits of artificial intelligence in human resource management.
4. To study the challenges of artificial intelligence in human resource department.

4. Research Methodology

The research paper is descriptive and has employed secondary data in the research. The secondary data is collected from academic papers, written articles, classified directories, HR forums and survey results published by various research organizations.

5. Role of Artificial Intelligence in HR

Now a few days of HR department heading towards the digital revolution and using different methods to simplify resources through the use of big data analysis, artificial intelligence, and cloud computing. Many companies use artificial intelligence or digital HR technology such as chat box, machine learning, and robot process automation in human resource management to facilitate recruiting, training, on-board, and interviews, etc. So there is the role of artificial intelligence in managing human resources;

- ✓ **Recruitment:** - The researcher in his paper defined that artificial intelligence is used by

only 40 percent of companies and industries. Organizations such as SAT, Facebook, and GE use digital technologies in screening, interviewing, and identifying the new talent in an organizational recruitment process. The application can be examined by an AI recruitment manager and the candidate can get a quick response. The chat box device or automated answering machine plays an important role in addressing the queries and problems surrounding an organization's recruitment process.

- ✓ **Screening and Interview Process:** - Artificial intelligence is useful in automating the interview process by testing them with analyses of phrase or speech patterns. The online interviews can take place via any apps and AI also helps to enhance the applicant experience. Tools such as Amy and Clara are used to schedule interviews and work meetings.
- ✓ **Reduce Administrative burden:** - HR has to play multitasking roles in an organization where companies using technology and Artificial Intelligence try to reduce workloads. AI facilitates problem-solving and helps to improve HR productivity in an enterprise.
- ✓ **Selecting:-** The researcher has examined how AI human resource managers can trace the right candidate in a short span of time and technology will help identify the appropriate candidates according to the required skill sets.
- ✓ **Reduce Discriminations:** - AI is used to minimize favouritism today and can help to improve organizational accountability. The organization will pick the resume in such a way. Analysing job requirements can be using AI applications.
- ✓ **Increase Efficiency:** -Artificial Intelligence should be helpful in reducing employee turnover at work. Various robotic tasks were performed to improve workplace performance. Robotic tasks include data collection, reporting, data copying, identifying required data from available data, processing, data collection for HR and payroll systems, and so on.
- ✓ **Enrich workplace learning:** - Nowadays, computers and digital technologies will do behind the scenes functions in the industry. Through computers and modern technology, industries are able to handle data analysis and provide real-time feedback during training, alteration of course of behaviour based on progress, and responses which industries got. Use Microsoft 365 to save time, businesses help workers work and increase workplace productivity. AI tools such as Engazify (To provide feedback), Obie and Niles (To share knowledge), Wade & Wendy (To advance careers), and Duolingo (Learning Domain) are used (Amla & Malhotra, 2017).

6. Impact of artificial intelligence on HR technology

The umbrella term for the software and hardware it automates the organizational function of

human resources. The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is one of the most discussed and debated developments in the HR technology of contemporary times. In terms of profitability for HR practitioners, AI would be the tipping point according to recent forecasts. Many professionals have believed the computer would take away their work. There's really no need to be cautiously optimistic; it's forecasting the real effect of AI in HR and Talent Acquisition very early. Much like any other technology, if not properly used and with the correct strategy, the users can find themselves in trouble. Before we continue to talk, let's take a look at what AI actually means. Artificial Intelligence is the field of computer science where computers function like a human brain in a similar way.

7. Five Ways in which AI could impact HR Personalization/Onboarding

Each new employee has its learning habits, respectively. Those are not always supported by any onboarding and training software. Employee-related preparation and coaching also form one of AI's possible impacts. The machine-learning algorithm that allows suggestions for the film and restaurant will be used to develop similar functionality for new training employees.

The program will become even smarter with a set of more employee data, thereby providing better recommendations and more effective training.

- ❖ **Scheduling:** Imagine a world in which you have a machine to book meetings, schedules and order food without doing anything at all. Does that sound good for you? Let's get you introduced to Amy Ingram. Amy Ingram is a personal AI assistant whose mission is to remove the pain of scheduling. The systems such as Amy Ingram have become one of the common tools for interview schedule, performance reviews.
- ❖ **Candidate Engagement:** All teams lack sufficient recruiters and even the right tools to enable them to engage with their talents as often as they should. We can potentially use AI, which allows automating the sending of emails and also the status message. If done correctly this could lead to an increase in the performance of the applicant.
- ❖ **Prediction:** Assessing and forecasting potential turnover, employee engagement, and training needs, as well as other developments in the workplace takes a great deal of time, but this forms a vital component of HR. AI and deep learning must use the data to predict accurately and faster than ever before. The information provided to HR professionals could be invaluable in helping organizations advice on change.
- ❖ **Sentiment Analysis:** AI is another game-changer when it comes to analysing sentiments. Businesses with a large amount of survey data, as well as reviews and AI data will easily detect patterns in employee feelings. This also helps to locate geographies, offices, or teams that are in stressful conditions by monitoring their email and conversation feelings. This marks the beginning; development will come It marks the start; changes will be coming in the future.

- ❖ **Video Interviews:** The video-based interview is now used by at least 40 to 50 percent of businesses. Such videos are stored in the database and can be scanned by AI to assess the mood of the interviewee. It determines whether the candidate tells the truth or not; and other elements, such as the expertise, language, and level of education of the candidate.

8. The benefits and functional strengths of AI enabled HRM processes

Taking repetitive task automation and record accuracy to a whole new level of competence is a low hanging fruit that AI can deliver for your HR department. HR operations that affect an enterprise's output most dramatically are often much more detailed and complex. It's in those tasks that AI really shines. Here are some of the benefits AI already offers to cut edge HRM teams all over the world:

- **Hiring and Onboarding:** To find the right selection of applicants for an interview, cognitive approaches can accommodate exponentially more resumes. You will assess and shortlist a large pools of talent-through criteria such as expertise, principles, abilities, and results-to ideally suit the requirements of your organization. A well-crafted orientation plan is a must when choosing the ideal candidates – statistics indicate that this can improve retention by as much as 69 percent for at least three years.
- **Talent Retention:** In a new report, almost 60 percent of the businesses surveyed face talent retention problems. It is an unnecessary drain on company capital and reflects a highly costly loss of value painfully generated. To alter this situation, AI can track many tangible - and even somewhat intangible - parameters. From recognizing workers who need to be compensated by promotions and rewards, to tracking work-life balance, AI will help solve some of the main factors why talent is frustrated with its current job and work environment.
- **Training and Performance Analysis:** Changes in technology and processes are a constant demand which a modern company needs to tackle. AI not only helps HR departments develop and organize training programs for all employee teams, it can also automate the process by taking into account the needs, schedules and interests of the individual employees. As far as performance appraisal is concerned, AI helps define and expand on specific targets as well as the individual activities that will help to realize them. It not only offers very detailed supervision but also lets individual workers monitor and measure their progress. In addition to having a positive effect on efficiency indicators, this strategy has been shown to greatly improve employee engagement.
- **HR Chat box:** One of the most successful solutions, that is helping redefine employee engagement and enhance several key HRM functions, is the use of Chat box. HR chat box strengthen connections within an enterprise – and that of the employee to the company itself – thus positively affecting workplace engagement. AI and Machine learning chat box are a tremendous asset in constantly customizing employee-related data. We are further characterized by the sheer ease of accessibility, a medium which

facilitates instant and round-the-clock communication and full integration across multiple channels.

9. Benefits of Artificial Intelligence in HR

1. Reduce the pressure on company management workers.
2. This can assist in the selection of talent and determine the right applicants for the job.
3. AI helps to predict on-the-job success performance.
4. This can transcend human weaknesses, and function accordingly
5. There'll be less risk of error.
6. It will preserve the the workflow in a different departments.
7. Will be able to get reliable results from AI companies.
8. This would increase on-the-job employee involvement.
9. This would eliminate bias in decision-making behaviour

10. Challenges of Artificial Intelligence in HR

There's no question that we face a variety of challenges in our country related to robotics and AI.

10.1. No Dutch: "Because leading suppliers do not include a Dutch language option, it's not always easy to apply things to a Belgian context. In reality, Dutch isn't even among the top 20 languages possible. That's making learning machines very difficult.

10.2. Legal aspects: "If a robot does anything wrong, who's liable?"

10.3. Change management: "We're in the midst of a change in culture from physical labour to intellectual work. AI and robotics have long had a bad reputation-to take over the work of humans but that's no longer the case. In reality, they help quicker, more effective, and more substantiated decision-making, for example by rating suppliers – just as we already do on Trip Advisor with holiday resorts and accommodation.

10.4. Ethical aspect: "You could also do the same in the workplace theoretically by screening people like consultants and job applicants before actually inviting them to see you. The problem is whether this is really allowed, not only in terms of privacy but also in terms of ethics. How far can you go-and may?"

10.5. Learning on the job: "Working with an exoskeleton or with robots or AI in general, has a significant impact on the on-the-job learning and training of people. You have to offer

Appropriate thought to that too.

10.6. Acceptance: "People tend to be swift to feel 'Big Brother is watching you!' Broad

acceptance at work of new technology is only possible on the basis of good communication and a carefully managed transition

10.7. Willingness of HR: "Technology, AI, and robotics are making significant headway. HR needs to be prepared and ready not only to deal with it but also to accept it. Involving business into the discussion is essential. Moreover, though HR is currently using technology mostly for administrative purposes – to test and track stuff – people need to really think about how digital technology will play a functional role in the workplace. That is, they will actively concentrate on it and take a constructive approach rather than a reactive one.

11. Conclusion

There's enormous potential for the manufacturing sector in a dynamic era. One problem facing industries is handling quality development. Increase speed and job routine for the majority of industries that implement new technologies. Many analysts and experts also suggest businesses to make use of emerging technology, artificial intelligence devices. Several organizations have used artificial intelligence and machine language in the human resource department environment where AI plays an important role in recruiting, choosing, hiring, performance monitoring, gathering employee data, delivering information in real-time, and delivering reliable information.

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